

Abstract:

In this report, the value of the ratio of matter energy to total energy, the dark energy density, and the very high value of the quantum mechanics vacuum energy density are calculated using the zero-energy hypothesis. The very high value of the quantum mechanics vacuum energy density is also predicted by the current contemporary methods of the cosmological constant problem. This report attempts to explain the true meaning of the very high value of the quantum mechanics vacuum energy density. The methods in this report thus provide a possible solution to the cosmological constant problem. The zero-energy hypothesis states that the total positive energy of the observable universe is equal to the negative gravitational energy of the observable universe. One assumption about the existence of harmonic oscillators that is made in current physics is that the energy associated with them is distributed uniformly throughout the vacuum. In this report, it is assumed that the energy of harmonic oscillators is actually not distributed uniformly throughout the vacuum at intermediate scales. The reason for this is because the generation of harmonic oscillators within the vacuum is associated with the generation of virtual particles, and these waves weaken with distance away from the virtual particles much like the intensity of an electromagnetic wave emitted from an excited electron within the electron cloud of an atom weakens with distance away from the electron. In this report, the calculated values of the ratio of matter energy to total energy, dark energy density of the vacuum, and the quantum mechanics value of vacuum energy density are 0.297, $5.986\text{E} - 10 \frac{\text{Joules}}{\text{m}^3}$ and $1.485\text{E}116 \frac{\text{Joules}}{\text{m}^3}$ respectively. These results use a value of the Hubble parameter equal to $2.3\text{E}-18$ /s. These results incorporate the zero-energy hypothesis and the fact that these results don't differ much from the actual values gives hope that the zero-energy hypothesis is true and that these methods are correct and provides a viable solution to solving the cosmological constant problem.

Nomenclature:

$c = \text{Speed of light} = 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$

$E_g = \text{Gravitational binding energy}$

$E_{\text{total in arbitrary volume}}$

$= \text{Ordinary matter plus dark matter plus dark energy energy in arbitrary volume}$

$f = \text{Frequency}$

$h = \text{Planck's constant} = 6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Joule} \cdot \text{seconds}$

$H = \text{Hubble parameter} = 2.3 \times 10^{-18} \text{ /s}$

$Ke = \text{Kinetic energy}$

$m_{\text{matter}} = \text{Ordinary matter plus dark matter mass}$

$m_{\text{total}} = \text{Ordinary matter plus dark matter plus dark energy mass}$

$\rho_{\text{matter}} = \text{Ordinary matter plus dark matter mass density}$

$\rho_{\text{total}} = \text{Ordinary matter plus dark matter plus dark energy mass density}$

$\rho_{\text{energy-dark energy}} = \text{Dark energy energy density of the vacuum}$

$\rho_{\text{energy-matter}} = \text{Ordinary plus dark matter energy density of the vacuum}$

$\rho_{\text{energy-total}} = \text{Ordinary matter plus dark matter plus dark energy energy density}$

$\rho_{QM} = \text{Quantum mechanics vacuum energy density}$

$r_{\text{arbitrary volume}} = \text{Radius of arbitrary volume}$

$r_{ou} = \text{Radius of observable universe} = \sim 4.4 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}$

$v = \text{Velocity}$

$\gamma = \text{Wavelength}$

The total kinetic energy due to the Hubble parameter within an arbitrary volume is given below. Only matter has kinetic energy whereas dark energy does not contribute to kinetic energy due to the expansion of the universe. Since velocity changes as a function of radius within an arbitrary volume, to get the total kinetic energy within that volume, integration is required.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ke &= \int_0^r \frac{1}{2} dm_{matter} v^2, v = Hr, Ke = \int_0^r \frac{1}{2} dm_{matter} H^2 r^2 = \int_0^r \frac{1}{2} \rho_{matter} (4\pi r^2 dr) H^2 r^2 = \\
 &= \int_0^r \frac{1}{2} \rho_{matter} (4\pi r^2) H^2 r^2 dr = \int_0^r \frac{1}{2} \rho_{matter} 4\pi H^2 r^4 dr = \int_0^r 2\pi \rho_{matter} H^2 r^4 dr = \frac{2}{5} \pi \rho_{matter} H^2 r^5 = \\
 &= \frac{\frac{2}{5} \pi m_{matter} H^2 r^5}{\frac{4}{3} \pi r^3} = \frac{3}{10} m_{matter} H^2 r^2 = Ke \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The gravitational binding energy within an arbitrary volume is given below. The existence of the Friedmann equation supports that this equation is correct which is mentioned further below. Gravitational energy includes both attractive gravity and repulsive gravity. This equation would represent a general relativity equation:

$$E_g = \frac{3Gm_{total}m_{matter}}{5r} \quad (2)$$

The Friedmann equation for a flat universe can be derived by setting the gravitational energy equal to the kinetic energy (both listed above). Any curvature in the universe would make these two energies unequal. The Friedmann equation for a flat universe ($Ke = E_g$) is used to obtain the total energy density of the vacuum. By using the Friedmann equation of a flat universe of eliminating the curvature term, the zero-energy hypothesis is being followed with this equation. This equation is a general relativity equation:

$$\rho_{energy-total} = \frac{3H^2 c^2}{8\pi G} \quad (3)$$

Using the zero-energy hypothesis, the ratio of matter energy density to total energy density can be calculated based on the value of the Hubble parameter. Satellite observations have already obtained this value but the zero-energy hypothesis allows for a method of calculation which will be utilized. The below derivations will be used in the script and will be compared to the actual value, testing if the zero-energy hypothesis holds up to actual observations. This ratio is solved for by setting the total energy of the observable universe equal to the kinetic energy of the observable universe which are both equal to the gravitational energy of the observable universe. On the scale of the observable universe, these three energies are assumed to be equal according to the zero-energy hypothesis:

$$\frac{3}{10} m_{matter} H^2 r_{ou}^2 = m_{total} c^2$$

$$\frac{3}{10} \left(\frac{4}{3}\right) \pi r_{ou}^3 \rho_{matter} H^2 r_{ou}^2 = \frac{4}{3} \pi r_{ou}^3 \rho_{total} c^2$$

$$\frac{\rho_{matter}}{\rho_{total}} = \frac{10c^2}{3r_{ou}^2 H^2} \quad (4)$$

The equation for r_{ou} is given below according to research:

$$r_{ou} \sim 3.35 \left(\frac{c}{H}\right) \quad (5)$$

When these equations are put into a script to iterate for the matter energy density, dark energy density, and the ratio of matter energy density to total energy density, the input variables are defined below:

$$H=2.3E-18 \frac{1}{s}, c=3E8 \frac{m}{s}, G=6.6743E-11 \frac{N*m^2}{kg^2}$$

Next, the results of the script are given below. ZEH means zero-energy hypothesis.

$$\mathbf{ratio} = \frac{\rho_{energy-matter}}{\rho_{energy-total}} = \mathbf{0.297} \quad (\mathbf{obtained\ using\ eqn.\ 4\ of\ ZEH\ which\ uses\ eqn.\ 5})$$

$$\rho_{energy-total} = \mathbf{8.515E-10} \frac{\mathbf{Joules}}{\mathbf{m^3}} \quad (\mathbf{obtained\ using\ eqn.\ 3\ (Friedmann\ eqn.)})$$

$$\rho_{energy-matter} = \mathbf{2.529E-10} \frac{\mathbf{Joules}}{\mathbf{m^3}} \quad (\mathbf{Total\ energy\ density\ x\ ratio})$$

$$\rho_{energy-dark\ energy} = \mathbf{5.986E-10} \frac{\mathbf{Joules}}{\mathbf{m^3}} \quad (\mathbf{Total - matter\ energy\ density})$$

The ratio of the matter energy density to total energy density and the value of dark energy density is a small error compared to the actual measured values of the vacuum, giving hope that the zero-energy hypothesis is true.

Next, an explanation for the very high value of the quantum mechanics value of vacuum energy density will be given using some assumptions. The first assumption is that the size of a particle in the context of wave-particle duality is defined by the wavelength which is supported by research. The second assumption is that the intensity of harmonic oscillators or quantum fluctuations is strongest at the location of a particle and weakens with distance away from the particle like how the intensity of an electromagnetic wave emitted from an excited electron from the electron cloud of an atom decreases with distance away from the electron. The current method of the cosmological constant problem assumes that the energy density of these harmonic oscillators is uniform throughout space, but in this report, it is assumed that harmonic oscillators do not have uniform intensity throughout all of space at intermediate scales. These

harmonic oscillators only have a very high vacuum energy density at the locations of virtual particles, and the generation of these harmonic oscillators is associated with generation of these virtual particles due to the Heisenberg uncertainty principle. Virtual particles are the particles associated with the quantum fluctuations or harmonic oscillators that satisfies the wave-particle duality.

To begin, the “size” of a virtual particle will be solved for which is related to its wavelength. The wavelength can be solved for using the quantum mechanics equation below which is the Planck-Einstein relation:

$$E_{total\ in\ arbitrary\ volume} = hf = h\left(\frac{v}{\gamma}\right), rearranging: \gamma = \frac{hv}{E_{total\ in\ arbitrary\ volume}}$$

For a volume of $1m^3$ of space, $\gamma = \frac{hv}{\rho_{energy-total}}$ (6)

To solve for the velocity, the Hubble parameter is used in an arbitrary volume of space associated with that volume’s spherical radius. A volume of $1m^3$ and its spherical radius will be used.

$$v = Hr_{arbitrary\ volume} \quad (7)$$

For a volume of $1m^3$ of space, $r_{arbitrary\ volume} = \sqrt[3]{\left(\frac{3}{4\pi}\right)}$

Next, the total energy within an arbitrary volume of space is concentrated to the “size” or “volume” of a virtual particle with wavelength γ . In this report, this concentrated energy density is assumed to be the very high value of the quantum mechanics vacuum energy density as the generation of harmonic oscillators are associated with the generation of these virtual particles. In $1m^3$ of space, the total energy is equal to the total energy density:

$$\rho_{QM} = \left(\frac{r_{arbitrary\ volume}}{\gamma}\right)^3 \rho_{energy-total} \quad (8)$$

When these equations are put into a script to solve for the quantum mechanics value of vacuum energy density, the input variables below are used:

$$H=2.3E-18 \frac{1}{s}, \rho_{energy-total} = 8.515E - 10 \frac{Joules}{m^3}$$

Next, the results of the script are given below:

$$\rho_{QM} = 1.485E116 \frac{\text{Joules}}{\text{m}^3} \text{ (obtained using eqn. 8 which uses eqn. 6 and 7)}$$

This value is not far off from the current value of the current cosmological constant problem when considering how many orders of magnitude that this calculated value differs from the actual contemporary value, giving hope that this report has a sufficient explanation of the true meaning of this value. The actual value associated with the current cosmological constant problem is 113 orders of magnitude whereas the value calculated above is 116 orders of magnitude.

It should be noted that the wavelength calculated in this section (1.11E-42m) is a few orders of magnitude below the Planck length even though the Planck length is the smallest possible length, so there is some doubt and uncertainty with these methods and the calculated value of the quantum mechanics vacuum energy density in this section. The current contemporary value of the quantum mechanics vacuum energy density uses the Planck length as a cutoff whereas the calculated wavelength in this section is used which differ in value quite a bit. However, according to research, the quantum mechanics value of energy density gets capped at the Planck length cutoff when dealing with lengths below the Planck length using the current contemporary methods of the cosmological constant problem due to black hole formation so that may explain why the calculated quantum mechanics value of vacuum energy density in this section is still close to the current contemporary value even when the calculated wavelength in this section is several orders of magnitude below the Planck length.

This report uses equations from quantum mechanics (Planck-Einstein relation – eqn. 6) and general relativity (Friedmann equation – eqn. 3), so it is possible that quantum mechanics and general relativity have been successfully bridged in this report but that is not 100% certain.